

AUGMENTED AND MIXED REALITY FOR DEMONSTRATION IN E-COMMERCE

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Abstract: *Retail presents a number of opportunities for AR, particularly when it comes to ecommerce. As much as people have gotten used to the idea of ecommerce, there are still some purchases for which we need a little bit more contextual information. That can be a barrier to selling certain product categories online.*

Keywords: *augmented reality, mixed reality, demonstration in e-commerce.*

The terms “augmented reality” and “virtual reality” are often used interchangeably, but they are actually very different. VR is fully immersive, while AR simply augments the real world. Augmented reality simply augments a world that already exists and that can be perceived, to some extent. Virtual reality, on the other hand — like Meta's Oculus Quest — is an immersive experience that lands user in a world completely of artificial creation. It typically cannot be seen and are not meant to experience the real world.

Augmented reality technology is really starting to take off, and advertisers — in retail or otherwise — are taking notice. Let's look at some of the numbers to prove it:

- Global AR advertising revenue, which topped out at half a billion dollars in 2019, grew to \$1.41 billion in 2020.
- One AR research firm projects that advertising revenue could top \$8 billion by the end of 2024.
- eMarketer estimated that more than 43 million people in the U.S. would use social network AR at least once a month in 2020. That's almost 21% of social network users.

- Overall, more than 83 million people in the U.S. will use AR on some kind of device at least once per month, and eMarketer expects this number to rise to 95.1 million by 2022.

- As of June 2020, 35% of U.S. respondents said they'd used AR to visualize furniture or vehicle customizations.

- A June 2020 survey of U.S. retailers showed that 20% expected to invest in AR or VR for their company's online store, up from just 8% six months prior.

5G availability is expected to increase retailer interest in AR and VR experimentation because of the improvement in bandwidth.

How Ecommerce Businesses Are Using Augmented Reality

AR allows ecommerce customers to preview products or experience services in their own environment and on their own time, before electing to make a purchase. Using AR, your customers can preview products and be more likely to pick the right product the first time.

1. Virtual try-on solutions.

AR helps online shoppers understand what they're buying and how the items will work for them. There are applications like this for clothing, makeup, accessories and even eyeglasses.

2. Preview placement.

Preview placement gives customers a real-time glimpse of what a product will look like when placed in their own environment.

3. Interactive user manuals.

An interactive user manual responds to user actions, providing on-page contextual support when using a piece of software, website, or application. Many AR user manual apps scan the product and indicate the buttons in the real-life environment using graphical arrows and animations with text.

4. Social media filters.

Over the years there's been a rise in the number of brands jumping on the AR bandwagon through social media filters.

Here are some of the benefits:

- It's a great way to showcase a new product by enabling people to test out how it'll look on them.

- The novelty factor of AR filters can help boost audience engagement and encourage people to tag you in their content.

- The "wow" factor can help stand out from the crowd of brands on social media and showcase what makes retailer special.

Mixed Reality in the simplest of terms can be described as the merge of real and virtual worlds to create an alternate environment for the end-user. In the new environment created by mixed Reality, virtual and real objects coexist at the same time and interact with each other to empower the user with unique

abilities. The technologies that are currently being used to render mixed Reality are AR or Augmented Reality, VR or Virtual Reality as well as Immersive Technology. In a mixed reality environment, users can interact with both virtual and physical objects. This allows users to manipulate virtual objects using their hands and other tools as they would in real life.

As a relatively new technology, there aren't currently many use cases around mixed reality applications. But with innovations on the horizon, this could change. Companies are primarily finding it to be useful in:

- Prototyping products in virtual spaces
- Assisting with design modeling
- Engineering

In the world of eCommerce, mixed reality could become more prevalent. It can act as a means of enabling consumers to get a sense of a product's look and feel before buying. VR can transport customers to the store, AR for eCommerce can let people view the product, and mixed reality would enable customers to physically manipulate different products, focusing more on the "feel" of the product. In contrast, VR puts you in a completely virtual environment but requires specific equipment: a VR headset and controllers. VR is widely used in sports training and flight simulation, to say nothing of games, of course. Built on these two realities, mixed reality apps allow you to manipulate and interact with elements of both the real and the digital world. For example, you can take a virtual box from your real bedside table, open it, and see what's inside. MR is a kind of immersive AR, no longer tied to a limited screen or viewer. Instead, it uses special equipment: a headset or glasses with controllers, just like VR. By using smart glasses and other tech, consumers may even be able to browse a physical store while interacting with various virtual components and interfaces. This effectively combines the two worlds into one. However, it may be a while before we see mixed reality become as integrated as VR and AR.

Conclusion

Immersive technologies have the power to break down barriers to enhanced learning, collaboration, knowledge sharing, remote work, and many more. Some mixed reality apps are more accessible than others, like virtual games, for example. Yet mixed reality can and will serve more serious purposes. It's already outgrown its introductory phase and has moved into developing the stability and functionality needed for widespread personal and commercial use.

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